

Computation of Sum of Optimized Binomial Coefficients and Application in Computational Science and Engineering

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Abstract: Computational science and Engineering is a rapidly growing multi-and inter-disciplinary area where science, engineering, computation, mathematics, and collaboration uses advance computing capabilities to understand and solve the most complex real life problems. In this article, a methodological advance is developed as an application for the researchers working in computer and computational engineering.

Keywords: combinatorics, binomial coefficient, computation

1. Introduction

V_n^n is a binomial coefficient with similar number of both subscript and superscript and its result is $V_n^n = 2V_{n-1}^n$. Before proving this result, we can understand the traditional binomial coefficient and optimized binomial coefficient [1 – 6] given below:

Traditional binomial coefficient: $nC_r = \binom{n}{r} = \frac{n!}{r!(n-r)!}, n, r \in N \cup \{0\} \ \& \ N = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Optimized binomial coefficient: $V_r^n = \frac{(r+1)(r+2)\dots(r+n)}{n!}, (n \geq 1 \ \& \ r \geq 0 \in N)$.

Here, $V_r^{n-r} = nC_r = nC_{n-r}$ and $V_r^n = pC_r$, where $p = n + r$.

$$V_n^0 = V_0^n = nC_0 = nC_n = 1 \ \& \ V_0^0 = 0C_0 = \frac{0!}{0!} = 1.$$

2. Computation of Binomial Coefficients

Proof of the result of a binomial coefficient [1 – 6] with similar number of both subscript and superscript, $V_n^n = 2V_{n-1}^n$, is

$$V_n^n = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)\dots 2n}{n!} = 2V_{n-1}^n \ \text{and} \ V_n^n = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{(n+i)}{n!} \ \& \ V_{n-1}^n = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{(n-1+i)}{n!}.$$

The following theorem is based on the computation of sum of binomial coefficients [1 -6] with similar numbers of both subscripts and superscripts:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Theorem: } & \prod_{i=1}^1 \frac{(1+i)}{1!} + \prod_{i=1}^2 \frac{(2+i)}{2!} + \prod_{i=1}^3 \frac{(3+i)}{3!} + \dots + \prod_{i=1}^{n-1} \frac{(n-1+i)}{(n-1)!} + \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{(n+i)}{n!} = \\ & 2 \left(\prod_{i=1}^1 \frac{(0+i)}{1!} + \prod_{i=1}^2 \frac{(1+i)}{2!} + \prod_{i=1}^3 \frac{(2+i)}{3!} + \dots + \dots + \prod_{i=1}^{n-1} \frac{(n-2+i)}{(n-1)!} + \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{(n-1+i)}{n!} \right) \\ & \Rightarrow \sum_{j=1}^n \prod_{i=1}^j \frac{(j+i)}{j!} = 2 \sum_{j=1}^n \prod_{i=1}^j \frac{(j-i+i)}{j!}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof: $V_1^1 + V_2^2 + V_3^3 + V_n^n = 2(V_0^1 + V_1^2 + V_2^3 + \dots + V_{n-1}^n) \Rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^n V_i^i = 2 \sum_{i=1}^n V_{i-1}^i.$

It is understood that $V_n^n = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{(n+i)}{n!}$ and $V_{n-1}^{n-1} = \prod_{i=1}^{n-1} \frac{(n+i)}{(n-1)!}$. Now, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \prod_{i=1}^1 \frac{(1+i)}{1!} + \prod_{i=1}^2 \frac{(2+i)}{2!} + \prod_{i=1}^3 \frac{(3+i)}{3!} + \dots + \prod_{i=1}^{n-1} \frac{(n-1+i)}{(n-1)!} + \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{(n+i)}{n!} = \\ & 2 \left(\prod_{i=1}^1 \frac{(0+i)}{1!} + \prod_{i=1}^2 \frac{(1+i)}{2!} + \prod_{i=1}^3 \frac{(2+i)}{3!} + \dots + \dots + \prod_{i=1}^{n-1} \frac{(n-2+i)}{(n-1)!} + \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{(n-1+i)}{n!} \right) \\ & \Rightarrow \sum_{j=1}^n \prod_{i=1}^j \frac{(j+i)}{j!} = 2 \sum_{j=1}^n \prod_{i=1}^j \frac{(j-i+i)}{j!}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

3. Conclusion

In this article, a theorem has been constituted based on the computation of optimized binomial coefficients with similar numbers of both subscripts and superscripts. This theorem is a sort of methodological advance and application [7] used in theoretical computer science and computational science and Engineering.

References

- [1] Annamalai C (2020) "Optimized Computing Technique for Combination in Combinatorics", hal-0286583. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/9p4ek>.
- [2] Annamalai C (2020) "Novel Computing Technique in Combinatorics", hal-02862222. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/m9re5>.
- [3] Annamalai C (2022) "Comparison between Optimized and Traditional Combinations of Combinatorics", OSF Preprints. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/2qdyz>.
- [4] Annamalai C (2022) "Novel Binomial Series and its Summations", Authorea Preprints. <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.164933885.53684288/v2>.
- [5] Annamalai C (2022) "Combinatorial Relation of Optimized Combination with Permutation", Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6341590>.
- [6] Annamalai C (2022) "Annamalai's Binomial Identity and Theorem", SSRN. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4097907>.
- [7] Annamalai C (2010) "Application of Exponential Decay and Geometric Series in Effective Medicine", Advances in Bioscience and Biotechnology, Vol. 1(1), pp 51-54. <https://doi.org/10.4236/abb.2010.11008>.